

Integrated pest management—diseases

Occurrence of teleomorph of *Fusarium graminearum* Schwabe, the causal agent of rice scab, in India

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Fusarium graminearum Schwabe is one of the causal organisms of rice scab

(RSc). We collected black fungal fruiting bodies from completely rotted tissue of the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the panicles of rice variety Leima Phou during November 1993 in research plots of the College of Agriculture and in nearby farmers' fields (Fig. 1).

Fruiting bodies were separated from the rotted tissues, purified, and placed on potato dextrose agar to isolate the fungus. Leima Phou was inoculated at

booting with 5-d-old culture to prove pathogenicity.

We compared the conidial state (anamorph) of the fungus with those of pure cultures of *F. graminearum* and two other causal agents of RSc, *F. moniliforme* and *F. avenaceum*. We also studied the morphological characteristics of the perfect state (teleomorph) of the fungus from the diseased specimens.

The perithecia are superficial, spherical to ovoid, dark brown, and mostly $60-200 \times 60-192 \mu\text{m}$ in dimension. They have cylindrical to club-shaped asci, often slightly curved with a short stripe, and a thin undifferentiated wall measuring $60-83 \times 4-12 \mu\text{m}$. They have 8 distichous to obliquely monostichous ascospores. Ascospores are hyaline, curved fusoid with rounded ends, with 2-3 septate, measuring $19-28 \times 5-8 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 2).

The perithecial characteristics of the fungus were identified as *Gibberella zeae* (Schw.) Petch, the teleomorph of *F. graminearum*, which has been reported in the literature on a range of gramineous hosts except rice. The occurrence of the teleomorph of *F. graminearum* on rice constitutes the first report from India. ■

1. Black colored fruiting bodies of *Gibberella zeae* on rotted portions of a flagleaf sheath.

2. Asci of *G. zeae* outside the perithecium. The ascospores are diagonally oriented in each ascus.

Rice hull ash applied to soil reduces leaf blast incidence

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Leaf blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious disease that can severely damage rice at the seedling stage. We investigated the effect of applying rice hull ash (RHA) to the soil in the seedbed on the incidence of leaf blast. The pot experiments were conducted in a greenhouse at ARS during the 1992 and 1993 wet seasons. Black to gray RHA (81.0% SiO₂), prepared by burning rice hulls in an open field, was amorphous with no peaks observed in X-ray

1. X-ray diffraction pattern of rice hull ash.

diffraction (XRD) patterns (Fig. 1). Only the amorphous form of SiO₂ is absorbed by plants. Crystalline SiO₂, from white or pink RHA, is not available for plant uptake.

The RHA was applied to a sandy loam soil on an area basis at 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 kg/m². The treatments were replicated six times on two highly susceptible rice cultivars: Early Kolapi 70 and Chimansal 39. A conidial suspension of *P. oryzae* was sprayed on the seedlings at night 15 d after sowing (DAS). The plants' reactions to blast were scored using the *Standard*

evaluation system for rice (0-9 scale) at 30 and 45 DAS.

Applying RHA to the soil in the seedbed had a marked prophylactic effect on rice blast in the seedlings compared with the control where no RHA was applied (Fig. 2). RHA greatly reduced the

2. Effect of rice hull ash applied to soil on leaf blast incidence in rice seedlings.^a 1992-93.

^a scores based on *Standard evaluation system for rice*, 0-9 scale. ^b DAS = d after sowing.

severity of the infection for both cultivars. For Early Kolapi-70, the RHA at 1.0 and 2.0 kg/m² was effective in controlling the disease at 30 DAS, with the seedlings still moderately resistant up to 45 DAS. For Chimansal 39, the seedlings treated with 1.0 and 2.0 kg RHA/m² were resistant to blast up to 45 DAS. The increased resistance to blast could be attributed to the increase in the SiO₂ content of the seedlings (Fig. 2) from the RHA.

The results demonstrate that applying black or gray RHA at 1.0 kg/m² to the seedbed can protect rice seedlings from leaf blast damage without using fungicides, thus helping to protect the environment. (Note: The use of rice hull-fired stoves, such as the FAO-promoted Vietnamese Lò Trâu or the IRRI-designed Ipa-Qalan cookstoves, by farmers for domestic cooking can facilitate collection of RHA.) ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Effect of some fungicides on *Metarrhizium* sp. Sorok: an entomopathogen on insect pests of rice and pulses

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A naturally existing entomophagous fungus, *Metarrhizium* sp. Sorok, was identified in adult brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål), and larvae of armyworm *Spodoptera litura* (F). The insects are important pests of rice and pulses, respectively. Legumes are predominantly cultivated after rice in the dry zone of Sri Lanka. It was observed that the fungicides frequently used to control diseases in a rice - pulse cropping system influenced the development of *Metarrhizium* sp. A bioassay method was used to understand the effects of commonly used fungicides on the development of *Metarrhizium* sp.

Effect of fungicide treatments on *Metarrhizium* sp.^a

Treatment	Concentration (ppm)	Mycelial growth of <i>Metarrhizium</i> sp. (cm) ^b	
Control	0	7.2	fgh
Propineb	100	7.7	bcd
	500	7.3	efg
	1000	7.3	efg
Mancozeb	100	7.3	efg
	500	7.4	def
	1000	6.6	ijk
Cuprous oxide	100	7.7	bcd
	500	7.7	bcd
	1000	7.8	abc
Metalaxyl and mancozeb	100	7.7	bcd
	500	7.6	cde
	1000	7.3	efg
Benomyl	100	0.6	n
	500	0.6	n
	1000	0.6	n
Edifenphos	100	6.8	ij
	500	5.4	l
	1000	4.1	m
Sulfur	100	8.0	ab
	500	7.0	ghi
	1000	6.6	ijk
Captan	100	8.1	a
	500	7.8	abc
	1000	7.7	bcd

^a Mean of four replications. ^b In a column, means followed by common letters are not significantly different at 5% by DMRT.